

Parasitization of azolla caterpillar, Mandya, India.

Sep 1983	Parasitization (%)		
	<i>Apanteles</i> sp.	<i>B. excarinata</i>	<i>Xanthopimpla</i> sp.
Wk1	30	8	1
Wk2	35	9	1
Wk3	43	11	0
Wk4	50	14	4
Mean	40	10	1

aquatic larva forms a tubular structure by folding the azolla and feeds on azolla fronds.

Infestation was slight in Jul, but by Sep 40-45% of the azolla was infested with the caterpillars.

Well-developed larvae and pupae were collected in the field at weekly intervals to identify natural enemies. Larval parasitization by *Apanteles* sp.

(Braconidae) ranged from 30 to 50% with a mean monthly 40% (see table).

The pupal parasite *Brachymeria excarinata* Gahan (Chalcididae) affected 8 to 14% (av 10%) of the caterpillars. *Xanthopimpla* sp. (Ichneumonidae) parasitism was about 1%.

Caterpillar population declined after Sep because large snail populations killed the azolla. □

Wet season population fluctuation of whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) in West Java

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WBPH *Sogatella furcifera* Horvath is a serious rice pest in Karawang, where Cisadane is the most popular variety. We recorded WBPH population fluctuations in 1983-84 wet season in Tunggakjati.

Biweekly sampling was by sweep net, 25 strokes with 10 replications. Captured insects were observed under a binocular microscope and WBPH and its spider predators were counted. At early growth stages, WBPH population was low and less than the spider population. WBPH population peaked 62 d after transplanting, then decreased. The spider population followed a similar trend (see figure).

WBPH and spiders /25 strokes

Number of WBPH and spiders at different ages of Cisadane rice in 1983-84 wet season. Karawang, West Java, Indonesia.

Parasite complex of yellow stem borer (YSB)

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We studied the parasite complex of YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walk.) from May 1980 to Jun 1982 at TNAU Coimbatore.

Egg and larval YSB parasites at TNAU Coimbatore, India.

Parasite	Family	Host stage affected	Mean parasitism (%)	Month of activity
<i>Tetrastichus schoenobii</i> Ferriere	Eulophidae	Egg	47	Dec-Jan
<i>Telenomus rowani</i> Gahan	Scelionidae	Egg	6	Oct
<i>Telenomus</i> sp.	Scelionidae	Egg	1	Jan-Feb
<i>Scelio</i> sp.	Scelionidae	Egg	1	Jan-Feb
<i>Exoryza schoenobii</i> Wilkinson	Braconidae	Larva	10	Jan-Feb
<i>Rhaconotus</i> sp.	Braconidae	Larva	3	Jan-Feb
<i>Amauromorpha</i> <i>accepta methathoracica</i>	Ichneumonidae	Larva	1	Sep

Four egg and four larval parasites were observed (see table). Egg parasitization was greater (47%) than larval parasitization (10%).

Tetrastichus schoenobii (Ferriere) was the predominant egg parasite. It peaked with 47% parasitism in Dec-Jan. *Apanteles schoenobii* (Wilk) was the predominant larval parasite. □

Pest control and management

WEEDS

Effect of time of herbicide application on rices of different durations

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We studied in 1983 the selectivity and effectiveness of four preemergence

herbicides in a lowland nursery at TNAU. Soil was a clay loam.

Short-duration IR50 (105 d), medium-duration Co 43 (135 d), and long-duration Ponmani (165 d) were the main plot treatments. Herbicides – 1 kg butachlor/ha, 1 kg thiobencarb/ha, 0.5 kg oxadiazon/ha, and 1 kg pendimethalin/ha – were applied at 5 and 8 d after sowing and compared to an untreated control. The field was puddled and pre-